

Spectrophotometric Studies of the Chelates of Iron(III) with Orthohydroxyphenones-I. Iron(III)-2-Hydroxy 4-methylbutyrophenone System

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The reddish-violet coloured complex formed at low pH by iron(III) and 2-hydroxy-4-methylbutyrophenone has been studied spectrophotometrically in a methanol-water medium. The results of Job's method and slope ratio method indicate 1 : 1 composition for the complex which has an absorption maxima at 530 m μ . The apparent stability constant of the complex at pH 2.4 and 30° has a value $\log K = 3.3 \pm 0.1$. The colour system obeys Beer's law in the range of 1 to 30 μg of iron(III) per ml.

The colour reaction of orthohydroxyketones and carboxylic acids with iron (III) has been widely used as a qualitative test of their presence in organic chemistry. However, it is only recently that these colour reactions have been a subject of some quantitative studies. Pfeiffer¹ studied the iron chelate of 2-hydroxyacetophenone. Jatkar and Mattoo² have reported the spectrophotometric studies on iron(III) complexes of salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetophenone. Agren³ determined the stability constants of salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetophenone complexes of iron(III) by potentiometric and photometric methods. Gandhi and Desai^{4,5,6} have reported the use of 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone, -propiophenone and -butyrophenone in spectrophotometric determination of iron(III). Our laboratory has been interested in studying the chelating properties of 2-hydroxyphenones and their oximes and as a part of this program it was considered worthwhile to explore the analytical potential of reactions of iron(III) with a variety of substituted 2-hydroxyphenones. The present paper describes the results on the composition, stability and other characteristics of the chelate formed by iron(III) with 2-hydroxy-4-methylbutyrophenone.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-hydroxy-4-methylbutyrophenone was prepared by Fries migration of 4-methylphenylbutyrate using anhydrous aluminium chloride in absence of a solvent. The product was separated by steam distillation and purified by distillation under reduced pressure. Standard reagent solutions were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of the reagent in pure methanol.

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2. S. K. K. Jatkar and B. N. Mattoo, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 607.
3. A. Agren, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1955, **9**, 39.
4. M. H. Gandhi and M. N. Desai, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1968, **43**, 338.
5. M. H. Gandhi and M. N. Desai, *Analyst*, 1968, **93**, 528.
6. M. N. Desai and M. H. Gandhi, *Micro. Chem. J.*, 1968, **13**, 500.

All the other chemicals used were of A.R. quality.

The stock solution of iron(III) was prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of iron(III) nitrate (Riedel, Germany) in about 0.1 *M* nitric acid. The concentration of iron(III) in the solution was determined by standard gravimetric and volumetric methods. Dilute solutions of desired concentrations were obtained, as and when needed, using this stock solution. All aqueous solutions were prepared in water twice distilled over alkaline permanganate in an all-glass pyrex unit.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer, using 1 cm glass cells. A Beckman glass-electrode *pH*-meter, Model H2, was used for *pH* measurement. All measurements were carried out at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ in a 50% methanol-50% water (by volume) medium.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Composition of the chelate: The method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁷ was employed to determine the nature of complexes formed in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol solution. Mixtures containing 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 mole ratio of iron(III) to 2-hydroxy-4-methylbutyrophene were prepared keeping the total volume 20 ml in each case. Since the preliminary studies had shown that the intensity of reddish violet colour was very sensitive to hydrogen ion concentration of the mixture, the acidity of each mixture was adjusted to 0.01 *M* with

Fig. 1. Job's Method (equimolar solutions).
 Total Molarity : $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ (Curves; A and C)
 Total Molarity : $8 \times 10^{-4} M$ (Curves; B and D)

respect to nitric acid. Absorbance measurements were carried out between 400 and 700 $m\mu$. The observations showed that in all cases only one complex with a λ_{max} of 530 $m\mu$ is formed.

In order to derive the composition of the complex, following two methods were used :

- (i) Job's method⁸ using equimolar and non-equimolar metal and reagent solutions, and
- (ii) slope ratio method⁹.

All the solutions were adjusted to the same solvent composition and acidity (pH 2.50).

Job's method of equimolar solutions was carried out at two different constant total molarities. The absorbance was measured at 530 and 600 $m\mu$ against the solvent. Neither iron(III) nor the reagent showed any appreciable absorption at these wavelengths. The results (Fig. 1) showed that the stoichiometric ratio of iron(III) to 2-hydroxy-4-methylbutyrophene is 1 : 1 in all cases.

The results of Job's method using non-equimolar solutions (Fig. 2) and of the slope ratio method (Fig. 3) confirm the 1 : 1 composition of the complex.

Fig. 2. Job's Method (Nonequimolar solutions).
Conc. of Iron(III) solution : $5 \times 10^{-3}M$
Conc. of Reagent solution : $2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$

8. P. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.

9. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.

Effect of variation of pH and time on the degree of complex formation : The absorbance of a mixture containing $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ each of metal and the reagent was measured at different pH values from 0.8 to 3.8 at $530 m\mu$. The results are shown in Fig. 4. It can be seen that

Fig. 3. Slope-ratio Method (at $530 m\mu$).

●; Iron(III) varying

○; Reagent varying

Conc. of constant component : $20 \times 10^{-4} M$

the absorbance changes markedly with pH of the solution. The pH range of constant maximum absorbance is very narrow, from 2.2 to 2.5. There was no change in absorbance over a period of 48 hr at pH 2.5.

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on absorbance of a (1 : 1) mixture.

Beer's law : A series of solutions, each with a pH 2.5 and containing the same concentration ($2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) of the reagent but varying (from 2.0×10^{-5} to $8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) concentration of iron(III) were prepared and their absorbance were measured at $530 m\mu$ (Fig. 5). The results show that Beer's law is obeyed over the range 1 to $30 \mu g$ iron(III) per ml.

Stability constant of the complex : The apparent stability constant of the complex was calculated from the absorbances data in Fig. 1 by the method of Mukherji and Dey¹⁰ and by Job's method⁸ using non-equimolar solutions. The average value of $\log K$ by these two methods is 3.3 ± 0.1 at 30° .

Fig. 5. Beer's law.

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